

Search for New Antimalarials. Part VII*. Synthesis of Some New 1, 2-Dihydro-*sym*-triazines

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Twenty-eight 4,6-diamino-1-aryl-2-methyl-2- β -substituted aminoethyl-1,2-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine hydrochlorides have been prepared with a view to testing their antimalarial activity.

The synthesis of dihydrotriazine derivatives carrying an aminomethyl group at position-2 of the triazine ring system has been recorded (Sen and Singh, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 643). The syntheses of dihydrotriazines (I) carrying a β -substituted aminoethyl group at position-2, have now been effected, the bridge between the substituted amino group and the triazine ring having been extended by one more methylene group with the idea of bringing about a change in the basic character and solubility of the molecule.

(I : R' = substituted amino group)

With the object of studying the variation of antimalarial activity with the alteration in the structure of the molecule, twenty-eight 1,2-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine hydrochlorides, recorded in Table I, were prepared by following two different routes.

In the first method the dihydrotriazines were obtained by condensation of the substituted arylbiguanide hydrochlorides (prepared from the corresponding arylamine hydrochlorides and dicyandiamide) with 4-dimethylaminobutan-2-one, 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one, 4-*N*-piperidinobutan-2-one or 4-*N*-morpholinobutan-2-one, following the method of Modest and Levine (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, 21, 14).

In the second method, condensation of the arylamine hydrochloride, dicyandiamide, and the above mentioned carbonyl compounds in one step afforded the desired dihydrotriazine (Modest, *ibid.*, 1956, 21, 1).

The dihydrotriazines were characterised through their picrates and differentiated from the corresponding arylbiguanides by the specific test.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Dimethylaminobutan-2-one, 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one, 4-*N*-piperidinobutan-2-one, and 4-*N*-morpholinobutan-2-one were prepared according to the methods of Mannich and Salzmann (*Ber.*, 1939, 72, 506), du Feu *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53), Mannich and Hof (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1927, 265, 589), and Herradence and Lions (*J. Proc. Roy. Soc. N. S. Wales*, 1938, 72, 233) respectively.

Dihydrotriazines : Method (I).—*p*-Anisyl-, *p*-phenetyl-, *p*-tolyl-, *p*-chlorophenyl-, *p*-bromophenyl-, *p*-iodophenyl-, and *p*-nitrophenyl-biguanide hydrochlorides were prepared from the corresponding arylamine hydrochlorides (0.1M) and cyanoguanidine (0.1M) by the general method described by King and Tonkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 1063). A mixture of one of these arylbiguanide hydrochlorides (0.025M) and the respective substituted butan-2-one (0.045M) in absolute ethonal (25 c.c.) was refluxed with occasional shaking on a water bath for 22 to 26 hours. The condensation was complete when the reaction mixture no longer gave a coloured precipitate

* Part VI : This *Journal*, 1960, 37, 643.

with cuprammonium sulphate (negative biguanide test). After cooling the reaction mixture in ice, the crystals of the dihydrotriazine hydrochloride separating were filtered, washed, and recrystallised from 50% ethanol.

TABLE I
(Vide formula I)

R.	M.P.	Triazine hydrochlorides.			M.P.	Picrates.		
		Yield.	%Nitrogen.			Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
R' = <i>NN</i> -Dimethylamino-								
<i>p</i> -OMe	213-14°	74%	24.46%	24.68%	196°	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₉	23.62%	23.65%
<i>p</i> -OEt	209°	81	23.65	23.70	179-80°	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₉	23.01	23.04
<i>p</i> -Me	234°	88	25.87	25.89	181°	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₉	24.31	24.38
<i>p</i> -Cl	243°	69	24.33	24.35	187°	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₇ N ₉ Cl	23.44	23.45
3-Cl-4-Br	224°	58	19.80	19.81	138-39°	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₇ N ₉ ClBr	20.29	20.44
R' = <i>NN</i> -Diethylamino-								
<i>p</i> -OMe	214°	66	22.68	22.80	190°	C ₂₃ H ₃₁ O ₃ N ₉	22.45	22.46
<i>p</i> -OEt	210°	69	21.98	21.96	176°	C ₂₅ H ₃₃ O ₃ N ₉	21.88	21.92
<i>p</i> -Me	224-25°	71	23.82	23.83	169°	C ₂₃ H ₃₁ O ₇ N ₉	23.08	23.12
<i>p</i> -Cl	229°	83	25.46	25.52	186°	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₉ Cl	22.17	22.29
<i>p</i> -Br	247°	70	20.07	20.13	136°	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₉ Br	20.65	20.66
<i>p</i> -I	247-48°	46	18.11	18.09	196°	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₉ I	19.16	19.18
3-Cl-4-Br	232°	52	18.55	18.59	171°	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₉ ClBr	19.50	19.56
3, 5-Di-Br-4-OH	221-22°	45	16.34	16.39	164-65°	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₉ Br ₂	17.83	17.87
R' = <i>N</i> -Piperidino-								
<i>p</i> -OMe	212°	70	22.01	22.07	194°	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ O ₃ N ₉	21.94	21.99
<i>p</i> -OEt	227°	73	21.22	21.30	187-88°	C ₂₆ H ₃₄ O ₃ N ₉	21.41	21.47
<i>p</i> -Me	229-30°	78	23.12	23.05	180°	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ O ₇ N ₉	22.57	22.62
<i>p</i> -Cl	238°	65	21.76	21.82	187°	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₉ Cl	21.78	21.82
<i>p</i> -Br	242°	70	19.51	19.56	185°	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₉ Br	20.22	20.26
<i>p</i> -I	258°	57	17.49	17.63	184°	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₉ I	18.80	18.84
3-Cl-4-Br	230°	40	18.08	18.11	199°	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₉ ClBr	19.13	19.20
3, 5-Di-Br-4-OH	219-20°	48	15.97	16.02	173-74°	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₉ Br ₂	17.55	17.58
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	261°	66	24.77	24.78	193-95°	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₁₀	23.82	23.81
R' = <i>N</i> -Morpholino-								
<i>p</i> -OMe	225°	71	21.95	21.96	184°	C ₂₃ H ₃₀ O ₃ N ₉	21.86	21.92
<i>p</i> -OEt	218°	65	21.12	21.19	167°	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ O ₃ N ₉	21.35	21.40
<i>p</i> -Me	245°	80	22.93	22.92	178°	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₉	22.51	22.54
<i>p</i> -Cl	251°	78	21.66	21.71	174°	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₉ Cl	21.78	21.74
<i>p</i> -Br	262°	62	19.40	19.47	187°	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₉ Br	20.11	20.19
3-Cl-4-Br	226°	53	17.95	18.03	168°	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ O ₇ N ₉ ClBr	19.07	19.14

Method (II).—A mixture of 3-chloro-4-bromoaniline hydrochloride or 3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyaniline hydrochloride (0.05 *M*), dicyandiamide (0.055 *M*), and one of the above mentioned ketones (0.075 *M*) in 95% ethanol (50 c.c.) was refluxed with stirring on a water bath for about 28 hours. The crystalline dihydrotriazine hydrochloride, which settled down on cooling the reaction mixture, was filtered, washed, and recrystallised from 50% ethanol.

Picrates.—Crystalline picrates of the dihydrotriazines were readily obtained on warming a mixture of a saturated 50% ethanolic solution of picric acid and the respective dihydrotriazine hydrochloride and cooling. These were recrystallised from 75% ethanol.

The m.p.'s, yields, and analyses of the dihydrotriazine hydrochlorides and picrates are recorded in Table I.